

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPLIANCE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF GENERAL EDUCATION WITH THE GENERAL LAWS OF MANAGEMENT AND TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article emphasizes that improving the quality of general education and finding management ways that determine the expected level has become the object of a perceived goal of social importance, gives a scientific interpretation of the concept of "quality of education" and shows the main reasons why the quality of education is perceived as an urgent problem of society in modern times.

Here, the authors propose an effective way of managing the quality of general education based on the idea of L. Bertalanfi's "system analysis" established in the 30s of the last century, the "system-structure" theory, which has become a development branch of dialectical philosophy, with the paradigm of "compliance with the general laws of management and teaching-learning process" put forward the idea of identification, argue the said idea by means of their personal experiences and generalizations on scientific research materials.

Keywords: efficient management system, systematic action, cognitive component, reflexive component, regulatory component, communicative component.

Relevance of the research topic

Education is such a system, process, value and result that most of its problems are eternal. This situation exists naturally (logically). Because education has an anthropological nature, its existence depends on the level of spiritual development of the objective reality determined by movement, time and space, during the sharing of spiritual development, the functions of the educator are bound to change in a form corresponding to the demands of industrial revolutions. Logically, the "Educational space" is subject to faster renewal in accordance with the emerging challenges of the technodemocratic-informational society. Despite what has been said, the problem of establishing an "optimal model" of quality education adequate to the challenges of modern times regarding the development of education, including general education, or its management should be kept in focus. Among the cognitive issues aimed at solving this problem, there is a special place for the issue formulated as "Compliance of the management of the quality of general education with the general laws of management and teaching-learning process". Therefore, we claim the relevance of the topic of the article.

Interpretation of the summation of research materials

One of the problems related to the development of education, perhaps the first one, is the establishment of quality education adequate to the challenges of modern times and its management.

The problems of the development of education at the desired level and direction (adequate to the challenges of modern times) affect everyone - from the people who make management decisions on a national scale, to heads of educational institutions, scientific

workers, authors of textbooks, methodologists, teachers, in short, those who organize the educational process at various levels. and finally, it worries parents, the whole community, makes them think, and forces them to look for solutions. Professor R.H. Mammadzade rightly noted that quality management in education today is attracting attention due to its urgency. [6, p.3]

In the field of education, quality is understood as the level of learners corresponding to pre-determined norms according to the results of education, and in general, the state of the education system. Quality is a philosophical category that expresses the certainty of any object, including education, and is an objective and general characteristic manifested in the set of its properties. Quality is a determinant of any process, thanks to which the process does not act like another process, but exactly that process and differs from other processes.

Historically, in order to evaluate the result and quality of education in educational institutions, the following qualitative (descriptive) methods were used: obtaining a forecast determined by teachers; assessment of students' morals in extreme situations that always occur in a student's life; assessment of students' morals in diagnostic situations thought and organized by teachers; evaluation of results according to the scale of criteria developed by the school itself; assessment of psychological indicators, all kinds of actions and activities used in the student's life: knows how to do (intellectual indicator); able to carry out (voluntary indicator); wants to relate (emotional indicator). [5, p.12-13]

After gaining independence, the attitude towards improving the quality of our education and working out the scientific basis of its efficient management models

has changed and the work in the mentioned direction has become more constructive. The modern concept of education considers the development of thinking as the main goal of the mental development of students. [1, p.54]

In modern times, the main reasons why the quality of education is perceived as an actual problem of society can be explained by two objective cases: 1) All subjects of educational activity - learners, parents, educators, managers and other workers at various levels who are engaged in effective management of the educational system are interested in building a quality education system. Recently, there has been increasing attention to building a quality education system for students. Both society and the state are very interested in providing quality education to citizens; 2) General education schools currently differ from each other due to the profiling of the training process, the application of innovative approaches, the effective use of new pedagogical and training technologies, the selection of new textbooks and teaching aids, educational programs, teaching-methodical complexes. The stabilizing role of the quality of education opens wide opportunities for effective management of the process in the conditions where such diversity has become more widespread in the education system in recent years. Therefore, the tendency of parents and learners to freely choose educational institutions is expanding, and the responsibility of educational institutions in preparing a competitive learner and fulfilling the requirements is increasing.

Managing an educational institution (including a general educational institution) is a complex process. In that process, the evaluation of the quality of education is one of the leading directions of the mentioned complex process. In this management, it is possible to talk about effective management and its scientific bases if the process itself and its purposeful characteristics, the compatibility of the process parameters with the final result is ensured. Of course, the result depends on the process itself, its quality organization. In order to assess the quality of education at each stage of the educational process from the point of view of management, grouping of its quality indicators, evaluation of educational results at periodic, near and distant time intervals during the course of the process should be provided, and the school's activities should be directed to these results. According to our subjective understanding, "educational quality management" should have a research character.

Scientific-pedagogical sources show that it is possible to group the pedagogical principles that ensure the effectiveness of quality management in education as follows: 1) The accuracy of information about the concept of "quality of education" as the main indicator of the efficiency of the managed system (if the managed object (system) is not clearly defined, then the meaning of management is lost, if the managed object is incompletely defined, then the management is ineffective, the educational system or education no positive progress is achieved in the activities of their enterprises); 2) Compliance of the effective management system of the quality of education with the general laws of management; 3) Compliance of the effective management system of

the quality of education with the laws and regulations of the teaching-learning process. [12, p.46-47] Based on our generalizations to the research materials obtained from scientific sources, we come to the conclusion that the paradigm of the effective management system of the quality of education should be considered "the expectation of compliance of management and teaching-learning process with laws and regularities".

The quality level of education implementation depends significantly on the form of its realization. The correct understanding of the concepts of "training" and "teaching" activities, which are important elements of the categorical apparatus related to education, fundamentally affects the correct realization of their functions.

It should be remembered that educational activity is multifaceted. Although training is a characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and teaching activities are essentially different events. Learning is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity, for example, play or work. Educational activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the personality. In the structure of educational activity, its following components can be distinguished: 1) educational situation (or tasks); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price. [1, p.150]

Professor A.O.Mehrabov writes that the analysis of the approaches used to manage the quality of education leads to the following conclusions:

- in order to ensure quality management, the meaning of that concept must be defined in advance for each managed object;

- it should be taken into account that the quality of education includes common elements common to the entire educational system, as well as special elements that characterize each managed object and have a corresponding property;

- since the quality of education has a complex structure, and there is no unanimous opinion about its management methods, it is impossible to give its general definition and broad interpretation for any educational system and educational institution. [7, p.214-215]

According to our subjective understanding, the "system-structure dialectical approach" should be focused here. When referring to such a methodological basis, it is taken into account that a part is a component that is part of the system and has relative independence. A system is complete, containing both elements and relationships between elements. The dialectical relationship of the whole and the part is actually the relationship that constitutes the structure of the whole, and in this sense, the structure acts as one of the important modes of existence of the whole. The dialectical unity of elements and structure is considered the main sign of the system concept. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of the system. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and functions. In principle, any system enters as an element and subsystem of another

system that has a higher, more complex completeness than itself, and must obey its emergent sign. [3, p. 104-107]

The correct identification of the factors characterizing the concept of the quality of education allows the management of the quality of the facility. According to Professor A.O.Mehrabov, it is possible to group such factors based on a certain logical basis. [7, p.215]

The requirements of the specific consumer using the educational system determine the main content of the quality of education, which is directly related to the functioning of the educational system. All parameters of the activity are subject to these requirements. In many cases, the education system has to work with several consumers at the same time. In such cases, it is very important to fulfill the requirements of the consumer, which requirements to take as the basis for determining the quality of education. The conducted analyzes show that in such cases it is logical to fulfill the requirements of learners. Such an approach meets the requirements of building student-oriented education. A large number of requirements that have already received public and state status in the applicable norms and standards should be summarized here. Learners should be grouped according to the same or similar requirements. These requirements include a certain part of the quality of education and allow determining its content.

Many methods of quality assessment are used in education. These can include: 1) licensing of educational institutions; 2) attestation of teaching staff and educational institutions; 3) intermediate and final attestation of students; 4) audit of teaching and other activities of educational institutions; 5) professional, competitions related to professionalism. [7, p. 216]

Among the presented issues, quality control in education and regular review of its status occupy a special place. In this case, the procedures for evaluating the quality of any process and determining new evaluation criteria for homogeneous objects are taken as the basis.

In the formation of the effective management system of the quality of education, it is of particular importance to give priority to the approaches related to management according to "process" or "result". Some approaches suggest that it is possible to divide the processes taking place in educational institutions into three groups - basic, controlled and auxiliary. Mainly scientific-methodical and scientific-research works; strategic planning for management, evaluation of the level of use of the results of educational activities of consumers; and the auxiliary can include material provision, financial and infrastructure management.

The results of the educational activity must fully correspond to the requirements of the consumer. The main issue here is to determine which results are considered as the main indicator of educational activity. It is known that since the object of interactions in education is the learner, it is logically necessary to give the results of education in the characteristics related to the learner.

Some researchers have determined the results of education with such approaches and based on the following: 1) students' knowledge, skills and habits; 2) indicators of the learner's personal development process;

3) developed effective approaches to eliminate negative effects affecting the teaching-learning process; 4) students' level of competence. Some researchers highlight the following as the results of education: 1) high self-awareness of personality; 6) physical and spiritual health; 2) his high education, his need for education and his habits; 3) high education; 4) the position of patriotism and high citizenship. Another group of researchers, as the result of education, considers the level of education of students who have completed their education as the main indicator, which includes the following parameters: 1) knowledge, skills and habits; 2) level of culture; 3) spiritual development, value indicators; 4) the possibilities of intellectual and physical development of the organism.

Researches show that the quality characteristics related to the subjects of educational activity play an important role in the modernization of education as a whole.

Circumstances related to the events occurring in the educational process create ample conditions to act as the main provider of the quality indicator of the teaching-learning process, while having appropriate effects on the participants of the process. Determination of training quality sanitary-hygienic, moral-psychological, educational process resource provision conditions, etc. depends on many factors. Therefore, in the educational process, such factors should be determined with special approaches and the limits of their influence should be defined.

The characteristics that ensure the efficiency of quality management in education, more precisely, the compliance of the quality management system with the general laws of management, have been partially investigated. [11]

The conducted analyzes show that without taking into account the laws of general management, the establishment of the education quality management system and the efficiency of quality management cannot be ensured. Such a conclusion is fully consistent with the "system-structure" approach [3, p. 104-107] and L. Betalanfi's idea of system analysis [9, p. 8], which was formed as an important branch of dialectics.

In creating the methodological basis of the effective management system of the quality of education, an approach that ensures "systematic activity" should be used. In general, the structure of the education quality management system should consist of a dialectical sum of the managing and managed subsystems. Informational information comes from the management subsystem to the controlled subsystem. The response to this information indicates changes in the managed subsystem. [4]

From the analysis, it can be concluded that in this case, the following cases may occur in the managed system that receives informational information:

- the quality of the managed subsystem's activity increases;
- there is no change in the operation of the managed subsystem;
- the quality of the managed subsystem's activity decreases.

The main condition for the effective management of the quality of education is the correct establishment of feedback between the managing and managed subsystems. In this case, the following requirements must be met: completeness, appropriateness, adequacy, objectivity, convenience, continuity, structuring. [13, p.34]

The structure of the administrative subsystem depends on the combination of factors that determine the meaning of the quality of education, and includes the following:

- methods of evaluating the quality of education;
- the processes taking place in the educational system;
- subjects of educational activity;
- the results of educational activities;
- the conditions under which the educational activity is carried out. [7, p.218-219]

With regard to the managed object (system), subjects of management consistently perform certain management functions: targeted analysis; to plan; control; revision and reanalysis. Among the functions of training quality management, the importance of planning should be emphasized. The achievement of each goal (conclusion as a result) depends on the selection of the methods of its implementation, the determination of the steps of the deliberate implementation of the methods of ensuring the consistency of the process. In fact, planning, in a certain sense of the word, consists of forecasting, programming and preparation of a work plan. [8, p.40] Plan indicators enable control. If the planning is done correctly, management activities are properly directed, good results are achieved and time is saved. In the education system, stable conditions are needed to achieve the normal learning process of schools and the development of the school, to achieve quality in education. However, in real life, the internal and external environment of the school is constantly changing, something is happening in the lives of teachers, and children's attitudes towards life are changing. It is often impossible to foresee these changes. They either hinder the implementation of the plans or expand the opportunities to improve the quality of education. In well-organized management, these changes are detected in time and changes are made to plans and work done accordingly. The control system obtains information about these changes through well-organized control or periodic monitoring. Management requires feedback. Management is impossible without it. If it is taken into account that the object of control is the quality of education, its importance increases even more. By the way, let's emphasize that there are many factors in the educational process and the quality of education can be improved due to them.

Achieving the quality of education, the structure of results-oriented management is formed from relevant operations. Here, the implementation of tasks and goals, the achievement of necessary results depends on the choice of management strategy. There are three main development strategies for the school to work in innovation mode, adopt and apply innovations: local, modular, systemic. [8, p. 56-57]

The local strategy involves the use of various unrelated factors that will affect the quality of education. Such changes are carried out on the basis of independent plans and certain results are achieved. They affect the development and progress of the school.

A modular strategy is used to solve certain problems complexly in a class or at a certain stage of education. In this case, the object of implementation of each idea is determined, the program of the experiment is prepared, its parameters are coordinated, applied, and the results are compared. If interesting results are obtained, it is studied and used. In this process, a team of like-minded and innovative teachers and managers to lead them are formed, which is of great importance in achieving quality.

The third strategy is the strategy of systemic changes. At this time, it is about the coordinated and planned implementation of all factors, innovations, and changes that can affect the final results in the management of the quality of education. The innovations applied here should be coordinated, and a development program of the educational institution should be prepared. The program for the reconstruction of systemic changes can be prepared when the school leaders are familiar with the application, organization, and experience of all pedagogical collective innovation processes, and master the methodology of conducting experiments. It should not be forgotten that the choice of strategy also depends on the nature, complexity, and volume of the innovations to be implemented. [8]

The quality of education can be understood as the relationship between goals and results. In order to achieve high quality in education, although it is complex and difficult, the goal that can be optimally implemented must be defined. Then, in order to achieve that goal, the shortcomings encountered in the analysis process are investigated. The following factors can be attributed to these defects: outdated, suboptimal, educational and development technologies that do not benefit the content of education, or have lost their importance, or weak involvement of students in the learning process, etc. After that, it is clarified under what conditions the defects that manifest themselves in the educational process have arisen. Mainly, the following can be attributed to them: shortcomings of scientific-methodical conditions; lack of high-level teaching staff; material and technical base does not meet the requirements; shortfalls in funding.

Ensuring quality in education and its effective management requires the introduction of new approaches to the content and methods of training in order to form new professional competencies in learners. In this case, it is necessary to include the following components in the structure of professional competences: cognitive; regulator (director); communicative; individual (personal); reflexive (involuntary). [8]

The conducted analyzes show that the components of professional competencies are formed as a result of the influence of reflexive processes. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to distinguish the following forms of the involuntary component:

- retrospective (critical understanding of past experience);

- situational (real assessment of the current situation, situation);
- perspective (foreseeing the consequences of the action, choosing the perceived option of the optimal strategy of morality, behavioral norms, etc.).

Since these components open wide opportunities for the learner to effectively implement reflexive processes and high reflexive self-organization, they should be taken into account in the educational process and the formation of such qualities should be ensured. [7, p.222]

Experience shows that it is important to ensure the quality of education and to prioritize the application of new approaches to its effective management, to prevent the mechanical transmission of ready-made knowledge, and to create appropriate conditions for the implementation of creative searches in the field of professionalism.

The quality of education is a category that changes from time to time, and it changes and updates according to the needs of social customers based on the challenges of our time. This reality requires that the monitoring of the results of education be carried out systematically, and searches for quality improvement be made. [12]

Continuous, realistic, relevant testing and evaluation programs provide teachers and parents with evidence of each student's learning outcomes and successes. Such objective information allows students, teachers, and family members to accurately determine the educational goals of students and plan the next level of education. The scores collected by the students are not enough to evaluate their activities and to determine the extent to which the students have achieved their goals. Students should have the opportunity to set personal goals, monitor their own personal development and reflect on the knowledge, skills and attitudes they have achieved. The means of evaluating the learning success of students should also have a teaching function and help them understand their learning outcomes. Inspection and evaluation criteria should evaluate the learning activities of students as both the result of the work and the process itself, and should serve to reveal the different and individual characteristics of students. Assessment should not serve to determine how one student reads in relation to another student, but should reveal the student's own level of individual development, and should not refer to external motives. [8] It should not be forgotten that the evaluation of student achievements is considered as a process of collecting information about the student's ability to acquire knowledge, use it, and draw conclusions, and serves the following purposes: 1) monitoring the student's progress (retardation); 2) making decisions in the training process; 3) evaluation of student's training results; 4) curriculum evaluation.

Assessment and learning processes are seen as two interacting aspects of education. Evaluation, which is a systematic process, is structured as an effective feedback tool between learning outcomes and stakeholders, including the following components: 1) Evaluation standards; 2) Data collection; 3) Assessment results. [2, p. 294-295]

By the way, it should be emphasized that the following principles are observed in conducting all types of assessments: expediency; mutual evaluation of achievements and educational opportunities; ensuring qualitative relevance and reliability of collected data, transparency, fairness, mutual agreement and cooperation in assessment; ensuring the developmental role of assessment results in training activities.

Monitoring and evaluation should be considered as the main tool for studying the quality of the pedagogical process and its individual areas. As in all management systems, in order to achieve the set goals in the training process, the process should be managed, evaluated at each stage, deviations should be noted, and clarifications should be made. In this case, the following requirements must be met: 1) the purpose of management must be clearly stated; 2) the starting state of the managed process should be noted; 3) the mechanism of influence on the process in the intended main transition states of the managed process should be determined; 4) systematic feedback and the processing of the data received as a result of it should be ensured, a mechanism should be created to regulate deviations during data processing. [5, p.11-12]

In order to establish a quality teaching-learning process in our education system and its effective management, it is necessary to ensure the development of the scientific, pedagogical-psychological, methodical bases of new pedagogical technologies, interactive learning methods, and bringing their results to the pedagogical process.

Scientific-theoretical novelty of the research

1) Improvement of the quality of general education, finding management ways that determine the expected level is shown to be a socially significant objective; 2) The scientific interpretation of the concept of "quality of education" was given and the main reasons why the quality of education is perceived as an actual problem of society in modern times were indicated; 3) The idea of determining the effective way of managing the quality of general education with the paradigm of "compliance with the general laws of management and the teaching-learning process" was put forward.

The result

An effective way of managing the quality of general education should be determined by the paradigm of "compliance with the general laws of management and teaching-learning process".

References

1. Alizade A.A. Psychological problems of the modern Azerbaijani school. Baku: "Pedagogika", 2004.
2. Subject curricula for grades I-IV of general education schools. Baku: "Education", 2008
3. Ibrahimov F.N. Essays on the basics of optimal proportions of algorithmic and heuristic activity in training. Baku: "Mutercim", 2022
4. Ibrahimov F.N. Lectures on general pedagogy (Textbook). Baku: "Mutercim", 2019.
5. Mardanov M.C., Agamaliyev R.A., Mehrabov A.O., Gardashov T.B. Monitoring and evaluation in the educational system. Baku: "Chashioglu" publishing house, 2003.

6. Mammadzade R.H. Quality as one of the leading directions in education. Baku: "Muellim", 2010, 170p.
7. Mehrabov A.O. Conceptual problems of modern education. Baku: "Mutercim", 2010.
8. Mehrabov A.O. Pedagogical-psychological bases of the realization of competencies in the information society. // "Azerbaijan school" magazine, 2008, No. 3.
9. Mirzajanzadeh A.X. Admission to the specialty. Baku: Baku University Publishing House, 1990.
10. Boloshov V.A. Systems of quality education. Moscow: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 2000.
11. Neimatov Ya.M. Education in the XXI century: trends and forecasts. M.: "Algorithm", 2002.
12. Potashnik M., Yambir E., Matros D. Management of quality education (under the editorship of M. Potashnik). Moscow: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 2000.
13. Shishov S.E. Monitoring the quality of education in the school. Moscow: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 1999.

МЕТА І ЗАВДАННЯ НАВЧАЛЬНОЇ ДИСЦИПЛІНИ «РЕКРЕАЦІЙНІ КОМПЛЕКСИ СВІТУ» В СИСТЕМІ РЕАЛІЗАЦІЇ ОСВІТНЬО-ПРОФЕСІЙНИХ ПРОГРАМ ДЛЯ ІНДУСТРІЇ ГОСТИННОСТІ

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META AND OBJECTIVES OF THE EDUCATIONAL DISCIPLINE «WORLD RECREATIONAL COMPLEXES» IN THE SYSTEM OF IMPLEMENTATION OF EDUCATIONAL-PROFESSIONAL PROGRAMS FOR THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті проведено аналіз основних сучасних вимог до якості підготовки фахівців для індустрії гостинності та індустрії туризму. Акцентовано увагу на фаховій підготовці кадрів для ринку праці готельно-ресторанного та туристичного бізнесу, який відчуває дефіцит спеціалістів нової генерації в усьому світі. Відзначено, що одним із шляхів розв'язання цієї проблеми є інноваційна академічна і практична підготовка за участі стейкхолдерів. Обґрунтовано роль і місце професійно орієнтованих дисциплін, зокрема, дисципліни циклу професійної підготовки «Рекреаційні комплекси світу» у фаховій підготовці бакалаврів з готельно-ресторанної справи та бакалаврів з туризму. Доведено, ефективність зміни традиційних форм проведення семінарів з предмету «Рекреаційні комплекси світу» на інтерактивні: співнавчання, взаємонавчання (колективне, групове, навчання у співпраці). Встановлено, що уніфікація змісту і структури навчальних програм та професійно-орієнтованих дисциплін, доцільна послідовність вивчення, наступність використання компонентів знань щодо загальних об'єктів вивчення є необхідною умовою підвищення якості підготовки фахівців для індустрії гостинності та індустрії туризму.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the main modern requirements for the quality of training of specialists in the hospitality and tourism industry. The focus is on the professional training of personnel for the hotel, restaurant, and tourism business, which is experiencing a shortage of new-generation specialists worldwide. It is noted that one of the ways to solve this problem is through innovative academic and practical training of bachelor's degree students in hotel and restaurant management and tourism with the participation of stakeholders. The role and place of professionally oriented disciplines, in particular, the discipline of the professional training cycle «World Recreational Complexes» in the professional training of bachelor's degree students in hotel and restaurant management and tourism, are justified. The educational component of «World Recreational Complexes» is part of the compulsory cycle of educational and professional programs for the preparation of a bachelor in hotel and restaurant management and tourism. The main goal of the discipline «World Recreational Complexes» in the system of training specialists is to study the conditions for the formation, development, and placement of territorial recreational complexes (TRC), familiarization with systems for organizing population activities to restore physical and spiritual strength: rest, recuperation, resort treatment, and tourism. It has been proven that the effectiveness of changing traditional forms of seminars for the subject «World Recreational Complexes» to interactive ones: co-learning,